

Technology Integration on Pedagogical Competence of Home Economics Teachers

Cyrell O. Elentorio

Abstract. This study examined the relationship between technology integration and pedagogical competence among 103 public secondary Home Economics teachers in Cluster 3, Davao City. Its primary objective was to assess the extent of digital tool use, lesson planning, technical proficiency, and learner-centered applications. Additionally, the research determined how these factors influence three critical pedagogical domains, specifically instructional strategies, classroom management, and assessment practices. A quantitative descriptive-correlational research design was used. Data were collected via a validated five-point Likert scale survey administered to random samples. Statistical analysis included mean scores to describe variables, Pearson's r for relationships, and multiple linear regression to determine the predictive impact of technological indicators on teaching quality. Results indicated a "High" overall level of technological integration and a "Very High" level of pedagogical competence. While teachers excelled in learner-centered applications, a notable gap was identified in their use of advanced online platforms such as Google Classroom. A significant moderate positive correlation was observed between the variables. Regression analysis revealed that all four indicators are significant predictors, with digital tool use identified as the strongest factor. It is recommended that the Department of Education prioritize ICT infrastructure and advanced digital training for educators. Teachers may integrate underutilized online platforms and align technology with curriculum standards. School administrators may establish technical support teams, while future researchers may investigate specific barriers to digital adoption. Teachers may increase their use of online platforms and learning management systems to bridge existing gaps in the variety of tools.

KEY WORDS

1. technology integration
2. pedagogical competence
3. home economics education

Date Received: March 30, 2026 — Date Reviewed: April 17, 2026 — Date Published: May 19, 2026

1. Introduction

In today's fast-changing educational environment, technology plays an important role in improving instructional practices in Home Economics (HE) in Davao City by enhancing learner engagement and creativity, and promoting the growth of 21st-century skills when used effectively. However, many schools in Davao City still face challenges, including insufficient computers, laptops, and smart TVs for classroom use, and unstable or slow internet connections that limit access to online platforms, videos, and other digital learning resources. In addition, malfunctioning equipment often goes unused because some schools lack sufficient ICT personnel to perform timely repairs and maintenance. Limited budgets and some teachers' difficulty adapting to newer digital tools further hinder effective technology integration. These challenges indicate that, despite the recognized benefits of technology, its successful implementation remains uneven across schools. This situation may also affect the quality of instruction and students' overall learning experiences in Home Economics classes. As a result, there is still limited research on Davao City that examines how the availability of instructional resources directly influences teaching effectiveness in Home Economics.

Technology integration in Home Economics education, while widely promoted, continues to present significant challenges in actual classroom implementation. Many teachers encounter difficulties related to limited access to reliable digital tools, inconsistent internet connectivity, and insufficient technical support within their schools (Blau et al., 2020). Moreover, even when technological resources are available, a lack of sustained professional development often hinders teachers' ability to effectively incorporate these tools into their instructional practices. This results in superficial or inconsistent use of technology, where digital tools are under-

utilized or misaligned with learning objectives (Ghavifekr & Rosdy, 2020).

Pedagogical competence, on the other hand, remains a critical yet complex dimension of teaching effectiveness, influenced by both internal and external factors. Many Home Economics teachers encounter difficulties in adjusting their teaching methods to accommodate the varied needs of different learners, particularly in integrating innovative, learner-centered approaches (Pagalilauan, 2021). Issues such as limited training in advanced pedagogical methods, heavy teaching workloads, and insufficient opportunities for reflective practice often constrain the continuous development of teaching competence. Additionally, the rapid shift toward technology-enhanced learning demands a higher level of pedagogical adaptability, which not all teachers are adequately prepared for (Collin & Quigley, 2021).

In this regard, HE teachers often find it challenging to incorporate technology into their instruction due to the fast pace of technological change, which demands continuous adaptation of teaching methods and competencies. The rapid emergence of digital tools and platforms requires teachers not only to acquire technical proficiency but also to redesign lesson plans, learner-centered, technology-adapted instructional strategies, and assessment practices to maintain pedagogical relevance (Ghavifekr & Rosdy, 2020). This challenge directly affects their pedagogical competence, as teachers must balance traditional skill-based instruction with technology-driven approaches that foster critical thinking, creativity, and learner engagement (Hattie, 2023). Without adequate training and institutional support, many HE educators risk relying on outdated practices, limiting their ability to fully harness technology for effective classroom management, learner-centered learning, and holistic assessment.

Globally, the movement toward integrating technology in education has produced uneven

outcomes, particularly within skill-based disciplines such as Home Economics. The International Computer and Information Literacy Study (ICILS) reports persistent disparities in teachers' ICT competence across countries, which can be attributed to variations in training quality, technological infrastructure, and institutional policy support (UNESCO, 2022). In developing areas of Sub-Saharan Africa, Asia, and Latin America, socioeconomic disparities still limit teachers' access to devices and professional growth chances, which hampers their capacity to effectively incorporate digital tools into teaching (Fraillon et al., 2023). In the context of Home Economics, these challenges are magnified, as teachers must not only integrate technology into theoretical instruction but also adapt it for practical, hands-on learning environments such as culinary laboratories, textile workshops, and entrepreneurship simulations. Consequently, while technological integration promises innovation in HE pedagogy, which enables learner-centered, interactive, and competency-based instruction, its potential is undermined by unequal adoption and insufficient capacity-building initiatives worldwide.

In the Philippines, the challenges of technological integration are likewise evident and further shaped by local educational realities. Research on teachers' instructional technology competence in higher education contexts, such as at Palawan State University, revealed that even instructors with strong pedagogical and content expertise still require additional training and institutional support to sustain high levels of technological competence (Dela Cruz & Javier, 2021). This suggests that their competence in more advanced applications showcased wide gaps in readiness for deeper technological integration (Clemente, 2020). Within the Philippine Home Economics context, such limitations are evident in various instructional environments. For instance, in culinary demonstrations, many teachers rely heavily on traditional face-to-face

methods because access to digital kitchen simulations or recipe design applications remains limited, especially in public schools with inadequate ICT facilities (Clemente, 2020).

In textile and clothing laboratories, teachers often use basic presentation tools like PowerPoint rather than computer-aided design (CAD) software that could enhance instruction in pattern-making and garment construction, thereby limiting learners' opportunities to engage with industry-relevant technologies (Dela Cruz & Javier, 2021). These examples illustrate that progress in technological integration is uneven, highlighting the need for capacity-building programs, adequate infrastructure, and ongoing professional development to ensure that Home Economics instruction fully equips learners with both traditional and digital competencies.

Locally, technological integration among HE teachers exhibits particular patterns. Many schools are implementing blended learning modalities, yet teachers often resort to traditional methods or basic digital tools due to limited training and infrastructure, which is consistent with the national trend. For example, at Davao City National High School, HE teachers may use PowerPoint for theory lessons but lack access to design or simulation software that could enhance practical Home Economics pedagogy. At Bansalan Community High School, intermittent internet connectivity constrains the use of interactive ICT tools, forcing reliance on printed handouts and demonstrations. These localized conditions illustrate how technological integration is constrained, which in turn may limit advances in pedagogical competence.

Existing literature establishes the significance of technological integration in enhancing teaching and learning across various disciplines; however, notable gaps remain in its application within Home Economics education. While international studies have examined how technology improves instructional strategies and learner en-

agement in general education (Al-Samarraie & Saeed, 2021), there is limited evidence on how these innovations translate to skill-based and practice-oriented fields such as Home Economics. In addition, although studies acknowledge that pedagogical competence is crucial for effective teaching, few investigations have explicitly linked technological integration with the multidimensional aspects of pedagogical competence, including instructional strategies, classroom management, and assessment practices, particularly in Home Economics. This lack of focused inquiry stresses the need for empirical studies that bridge technology adoption and pedagogical competence in HE, thereby providing insights for teacher training, curriculum design, and policy-making aimed at sustaining relevant and future-ready education.

1.1. Theoretical/Conceptual Framework of the Study—This study was primarily anchored on the Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK) Theory which explains how teachers integrate technology effectively by balancing content knowledge (what to teach), pedagogical knowledge (how to teach), and technological knowledge (tools to use). It asserts that meaningful technology integration requires teachers not only to be competent in their subject matter but also to understand how digital tools transform teaching strategies and learner engagement. For Home Economics teachers, TPACK guides the use of simulations, digital platforms, and multimedia resources to improve both practical and theoretical instruction. Studies emphasize that TPACK strengthens teachers' pedagogical competence by fostering adaptability, innovation, and alignment of digital tools with curriculum objectives (Schmid et al., 2021).

Another theory that supports the main theory is the Constructivist Learning Theory, which posits that learners build knowledge through active participation, collaboration, and real-world problem-solving. In the context of

Home Economics, integrating technology such as virtual labs, e-portfolios, and collaborative platforms aligns with constructivist principles by creating experiential, learner-centered learning opportunities. Teachers' pedagogical competence is enhanced when they use technology to scaffold learning, facilitate inquiry, and encourage learners to apply theoretical concepts in practical contexts. Research confirms that technology-driven constructivist environments promote critical thinking, creativity, and deeper engagement in applied subjects (Bond, 2020; Sailer et al., 2024).

Another relevant theory is Rogers' Diffusion of Innovation theory which explains how new technologies are adopted within educational settings. It highlights the roles of early adopters, organizational culture, and perceived benefits in influencing teachers' willingness to integrate technology. For Home Economics educators, the adoption of digital tools like online marketplaces, design software, or food simulation apps is often shaped by institutional support and peer influence. Research shows that DOI directly relates to pedagogical competence, as teachers who embrace innovative technologies develop more effective instructional strategies and remain responsive to evolving educational demands (Aboagye et al., 2021; Kerimbayev et al., 2023).

The conceptual framework of the study is shown in Figure 1. The independent variable is the technological integration of public secondary Home Economics teachers in Cluster 3, Division of Davao City in terms of the use of digital tools and resources, integration of technology in lesson planning, technological proficiency and skills, and learner-centered technology applications. On the other hand, the dependent variable is the Pedagogical Competence of public secondary Home Economics teachers in Cluster 3, Division of Davao City in terms of instructional strategies and methods, classroom management and learner engagement, and

Conceptual Framework Showing the Variables of the Study

Fig. 1. Conceptual Paradigm Showing the Variables of the Study assessment and evaluation practices.

2. Methodology

This chapter discusses the research methods in conducting the study which are considered strategies or techniques utilized in the collection of data evidence for analysis in order to uncover new information or create a better understanding of a topic. Contents of this chapter include the research design, research respondents of the study, research instrument, and data gathering procedures.

2.1. Research Design—This study employed a quantitative descriptive-correlational research design. This design was appropriate because the study sought to describe the current extent of technological integration among Home Economics teachers in Cluster 3, Division of Davao City, and their level of pedagogical competence across multiple domains, including instructional strategies, classroom management, and assessment practices. By using a descriptive approach, the research captured the existing conditions of teachers’ technological ability and teaching competence in measurable terms, providing a comprehensive snapshot of the present educational context (Creswell & Creswell, 2019; Fraenkel et al., 2021). Meanwhile, the correlational design allowed for the examination of possible associations between

the two main variables, which are technological integration and pedagogical competence, without manipulating them. This was ideal since both variables were naturally occurring in the school setting (McMillan & Schumacher, 2021).

Moreover, the design enabled the study to go beyond simple description by exploring predictive relationships. Specifically, it allowed the researcher to test whether certain indicators of technological integration such as the use of digital tools and resources, integration of technology in lesson planning, technological proficiency and skills, or learner-centered technology applications significantly influenced pedagogical competence. This made the research not only diagnostic of current practices but also explanatory of potential linkages that informed instructional improvements (Gay et al.,

2020; Lodico et al., 2019). Using a descriptive-correlational design, the study provided valuable evidence for educational stakeholders by identifying patterns and relationships that could guide future teacher development programs and the integration of technology into Home Economics education (Creswell & Creswell, 2019).

2.2. *Ethical Considerations*—This study adhered strictly to the established protocols and standard guidelines required for conducting research, particularly in managing respondents' data. The survey questionnaire, along with supporting documentation from the authors, was submitted for thorough evaluation. Following approval from the Ethics Committee, the researcher proceeded with the study.

Social Value. This study ensured social value by contributing to the improvement of teaching practices and educational outcomes in public secondary schools. By examining the relationship between technological integration and pedagogical competence, the research generated insights that informed teacher development programs, policy interventions, and curriculum enhancement, particularly in Home Economics which is a subject vital for life skills and sustainable living (WHO, 2021). The findings not only benefited teachers by identifying their strengths and areas for growth but also enhanced learners' learning experiences in Cluster 3, Division of Davao City, thereby aligning with the ethical principle that research must produce knowledge with practical relevance and societal benefit (Resnik, 2020). Ultimately, the study ensured that the knowledge generated was useful to education stakeholders, including the Department of Education (DepEd), school administrators, and the broader community. In the local community context, the study supports the development of learners who are better equipped with practical skills in food management, entrepreneurship, and household resource management, which are essential for improving family well-being and economic resilience.

Furthermore, by strengthening teachers' capacity, the study indirectly contributes to community development, as learners can apply their acquired competencies in real-life situations that promote sustainable practices and livelihood opportunities in the Davao Region.

Informed Consent. The principle of informed consent was central to the ethical conduct of this research, ensuring that all Home Economics teachers voluntarily participated with a clear understanding of the study's objectives, procedures, and scope. Participants were provided with a consent form detailing the purpose of the research, expected time commitments, potential risks, and their rights to withdraw without penalty at any stage (Beauchamp & Childress, 2019). The consent process avoided coercion by making clear that participation was entirely voluntary and did not affect their professional standing. Ensuring participants' comprehension was vital, especially in a diverse teaching workforce, and information was presented in plain language. This process upheld respect for autonomy and individuals' right to make informed decisions about their participation (Iphofen, 2022).

Vulnerability of Research Participants. Participants' vulnerability was considered a critical ethical concern, as Home Economics teachers may have felt professionally exposed when their pedagogical competence was assessed. Teachers might have worried about how their responses could be perceived by their superiors or colleagues, which could have influenced their willingness to provide honest answers. To mitigate this, the researcher emphasized that the study's purpose was strictly academic and developmental rather than evaluative, ensuring that the results would not be used against participants in any professional context (McMillan & Schumacher, 2021). Special attention was given to creating a safe environment in which teachers felt comfortable expressing their perspectives without fear of judgment, thereby safeguarding

their dignity and minimizing potential psychological stress or reputational risk.

Privacy and Confidentiality. The ethical principle of privacy and confidentiality was strictly maintained by protecting all data collected from teachers in Cluster 3. Participants' identities were anonymized through codes, and results were reported in aggregate form to prevent individual identification (Iphofen, 2022). All responses were stored securely in password-protected digital files accessible only to the researcher, while printed data were kept in a secure cabinet. Teachers were assured that no personal or professional identifiers, such as names, school positions, or contact details, were disclosed. This ethical safeguard built trust between the researcher and participants and aligned with international standards of ethical research in education (Resnik, 2020).

The Risk, Benefits & Safety. This study involved minimal risk, as it primarily required participants to respond to survey questionnaires. However, potential psychological risks such as slight discomfort or anxiety arising from self-assessment were acknowledged. To address these concerns, the researcher ensured anonymity and emphasized that there were no right or wrong answers, thereby reducing pressure on the respondents (Creswell & Creswell, 2019). The benefits of the study outweighed these minimal risks, as it generated valuable insights that could contribute to professional development, improved instructional practices, and informed educational planning. These outcomes support the continuous enhancement of teaching effectiveness, particularly in Home Economics education.

To ensure the safety and well-being of participants, the study strictly adhered to ethical principles such as voluntary participation, the right to skip any question, and the freedom to withdraw from the study at any time without penalty. The researcher maintained a respectful and non-threatening environment throughout

the data collection process to promote participant comfort and openness. As part of the contingency plan, the researcher was prepared to immediately pause or terminate participation if any respondent showed signs of discomfort or distress. Furthermore, participants were informed that they could seek assistance from school support personnel, such as guidance counselors, should they experience any concerns related to their participation. This comprehensive approach ensured that the study upheld the principle of beneficence and prioritized participant welfare (Beauchamp & Childress, 2019).

Justice. The ethical principle of justice was observed by ensuring fairness in the selection and treatment of participants. All Home Economics teachers in Cluster 3 were given an equal opportunity to participate, preventing bias in recruitment and avoiding favoritism or exclusion based on age, tenure, or school status. Justice also entailed that the potential benefits of the research, such as improved training and instructional practices, were equitably shared among participants and their schools. This principle guaranteed that no group of teachers bore a disproportionate burden of participation while others unfairly benefited from the study's outcomes (Emanuel et al., 2019).

Transparency. Transparency was ensured throughout the research process by providing clear and open communication with all stakeholders, including participants, school administrators, and relevant DepEd offices. Teachers were fully informed of the study's scope, objectives, and expected outcomes, while regular updates on progress and findings were shared with stakeholders in an accessible manner (Resnik, 2020). Transparency also involved accurately reporting results without fabrication or misrepresentation and acknowledging limitations to avoid misleading interpretations (Iphofen, 2022). Such openness built trust and ensured the accountability of the researcher to both partic-

ipants and the wider academic community. To further strengthen transparency, the results of the study may be disseminated through RMC's activities such as research colloquia, public forums, and stakeholder presentations. These platforms provide opportunities for open discussion, validation of findings, and feedback from academic peers and practitioners. Additionally, sharing the results through institutional reports and community-based presentations ensures that the knowledge generated remains accessible, relevant, and beneficial to all concerned stakeholders.

Qualification of the Researcher. The qualification of the researcher was essential to ethical conduct, as competence ensured the integrity and validity of the study. The researcher had a strong background in education and research methodologies, particularly within the field of technology integration and pedagogical studies, which ensured the capability to design, conduct, and interpret the study responsibly (Creswell & Creswell, 2019). Additionally, the researcher had completed all the necessary prerequisites to proceed with thesis writing. Moreover, the researcher was bound by professional codes of conduct and had undergone training in research ethics, ensuring compliance with institutional review board (IRB) or ethics committee requirements (Babbie, 2021). This ethical dimension ensured that participants could trust the researcher to act professionally and uphold ethical standards.

Adequacy of Facilities. The study also considered the adequacy of facilities required for ethical research conduct. Appropriate venues, such as school meeting rooms or designated areas approved by administrators, were used for data collection to ensure participants' convenience and comfort (Emanuel et al., 2019). Secure facilities for data storage, including locked cabinets and encrypted files, were utilized to protect participants' information. The adequacy of facilities also extended to access to com-

munication channels, such as printed materials or digital consent forms, ensuring all participants could fully engage in the process (WHO, 2021). This ethical measure ensured both participant safety and the reliability of collected data. In addition, Rizal Memorial Colleges, Inc. provided supportive research facilities such as a well-equipped library with access to academic journals, reference materials, and digital databases that aided in the development of the study. The institution also offered research-related resources, including computer laboratories and internet connectivity, which facilitated data processing, analysis, and documentation of the research outputs.

Community Involvement. Lastly, community involvement was considered a vital ethical parameter, as the research directly impacted the educational community of Cluster 3, Division of Davao City. Engaging DepEd officials, school administrators, and teacher groups throughout the research process ensured that the study aligned with community needs and priorities (Iphofen, 2022). This participatory approach respected the principle of inclusivity by valuing stakeholders' voices and fostering ownership of the results. Sharing findings with the community through presentations or policy briefs strengthened the study's impact by translating academic results into practical strategies for teaching improvement (Resnik, 2020). Involving the community thus ensured that the research was contextually relevant and ethically responsive.

2.3. Research Respondents—The respondents of the study consisted of Home Economics and Technology and Livelihood Education (HE/TLE) public secondary school teachers particularly handling cookery, bread and pastry production, housekeeping, dressmaking, beauty care, and handicraft from Cluster 3 in the Division of Davao City, which served as the research setting. Out of the total 138 teachers in the cluster, 103 were selected as respondents through

random sampling determined by Slovin's formula, ensuring that the selected sample was representative of the population while maintaining accuracy and feasibility (Tejada & Punzalan, 2019). The use of random sampling provided each teacher with an equal opportunity to be included in the study, thereby minimizing selection bias and enhancing the reliability of findings related to classroom practices and instructional quality (Daniel, 2019).

The respondents included both male and female teachers, aged between 25 to 55 years, which reflected a demographic group with sufficient maturity and professional exposure to provide informed insights on technological integration and pedagogical competence. On average, they had at least one year of teaching experience, which positioned them as credible sources of information regarding how long-term instructional practices interacted with emerging technological trends. By engaging teachers with this profile, the study ensured that the data reflected both professional expertise and lived experiences in the teaching-learning process (Saunders et al., 2019).

Furthermore, all participating teachers held at least a bachelor's degree in secondary education, which is a standard qualification that guarantees foundational training in pedagogy, curriculum design, and classroom management. This educational background strengthened the reliability of their responses, as they were equipped with both theoretical and practical knowledge relevant to the study's focus on pedagogical competence (Creswell & Creswell, 2019; Gay et al., 2020). Their specialization in Home Economics further ensured that the research findings were grounded in the realities of a subject area that integrates both technical skills and life-oriented instruction. By carefully selecting respondents who met these criteria, the study not only upheld methodological rigor but also enhanced the credibility and applicability of its findings to the broader educational

context of the Division of Davao City. Thus, the selected respondents represented a profile capable of providing meaningful perspectives on the effects of technological integration on pedagogical competence.

2.4. Research Instruments—Designing effective research instruments was a fundamental step in the research process because these tools provided the necessary means to collect relevant data from participants. Well-developed instruments played a crucial role in ensuring the accuracy and credibility of research outcomes by capturing the variables under study in a structured, systematic manner (Huck, 2019). They also provided standardized procedures for data collection, which enhanced the reliability of the results and allowed for comparability across similar studies in the field of education (Cohen et al., 2021). In the present study, the researcher utilized a survey questionnaire as the primary instrument for data collection, carefully designed to capture the two major variables of interest: technological integration and pedagogical competence of public secondary Home Economics teachers.

The survey questionnaire was divided into two major sections. The first section gathered data on the extent of technological integration ability of Home Economics teachers in Cluster 3, Division of Davao City, specifically in terms of use of digital tools and resources, integration of technology in lesson planning, technological proficiency and skills, and learner-centered technology applications. Items in the instrument were adapted from relevant and validated studies, such as Adeoye and Adeoye's (2020) research on instructional resources, to ensure appropriateness and credibility in assessing the chosen constructs.

In the process of interpreting its data, a five-point Likert scale was used in the survey, with five (5) as the highest and one (1) as the lowest. The scale, along with its corresponding descriptions and interpretations, was presented to guide

the analysis. The five ordered gradations, with their respective range of means and descriptive equivalents, were considered to ensure consistency and clarity in interpreting the responses.

Scale to Gathered Data on the Extent of Technological Integration Ability of Home Economics Teachers in Cluster 3

Range	Descriptive Equivalent	Interpretation
4.20-5.00	Very High	The Technological Integration of public secondary Home Economics teachers are always evident.
3.40-4.19	High	The Technological Integration of public secondary Home Economics teachers are often evident.
2.60-3.39	Moderate	The Technological Integration of public secondary Home Economics teachers are sometimes evident.
1.80-2.59	Low	The Technological Integration of public secondary Home Economics teachers are seldom evident.
1.00-1.79	Very Low	The Technological Integration of public secondary Home Economics teachers are not evident.

The second section of the questionnaire focused on determining the extent of pedagogical competence of public secondary Home Economics teachers in Cluster 3, Division of Davao City. This section was designed to assess how teachers demonstrated effectiveness in their pedagogical practices through indicators such as instructional strategies and methods, classroom management and learner engagement, and assessment and evaluation practices. These domains were considered critical components of effective teaching, as they encompassed the ability to plan, implement, and evaluate instruction that promotes meaningful learning experiences for learners. Similar to the first part of the survey questionnaire, a five-point Likert scale was used in interpreting the data, with five (5) as the highest and one (1) as the lowest. The scale, along with its descriptions and interpretations, was presented accordingly, and the five ordered gradations with their respective range of means and descriptions were considered.

Scale to Determining the Extent of Pedagogical Competence of Public Secondary Home Economics Teachers in Cluster 3

Range	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20-5.00	Very High	The Pedagogical Competence of public secondary Home Economics teachers are always evident.
3.40-4.19	High	The Pedagogical Competence of public secondary Home Economics teachers are often evident.
2.60-3.39	Moderate	The Pedagogical Competence of public secondary Home Economics teachers are sometimes evident.
1.80-2.59	Low	The Pedagogical Competence of public secondary Home Economics teachers are seldom evident.
1.00-1.79	Very Low	The Pedagogical Competence of public secondary Home Economics teachers are not evident.

To ensure the reliability and appropriateness of the measurement, items in this section were adopted from Stronge's (2019) framework on the qualities of effective teachers, which has been widely recognized and applied in educational research. The adaptation of such established indicators enhanced the validity of the instrument, as they were grounded in empirically tested dimensions of teaching effectiveness. This alignment guaranteed that the study's results reflected both theoretical rigor and practical relevance in understanding how technological integration influenced the pedagogical competence of Home Economics teachers within the context of Cluster 3, Division of Davao City. Moreover, the reliability analysis yielded a Cronbach's alpha of 0.757 across 35 items, indicating an acceptable level of internal consistency among the questionnaire items. This suggests that the instrument was sufficiently reliable for measuring the indicators of technological integration and pedagogical competence in the study.

2.5. Data Gathering Procedure—In the initial phase of the data collection process, the researcher prepared and submitted a formal letter of request for authorization from the Dean of the Graduate School to secure institutional approval for the conduct of the study. Upon obtaining this clearance, another communication was addressed to the Schools Division Superintendent of the Division of Davao City and routed through the appropriate channels, particularly the Office of Public Schools District Supervisors (PSDS) overseeing the identified schools. These formal procedures were necessary to ensure compliance with organizational protocols and to affirm the legitimacy of the research undertaking. Once the necessary permissions were granted, the finalized survey questionnaire was prepared for administration to the selected respondents.

Following approval and authorization from the concerned offices, the researcher proceeded

with data collection at the identified schools under Cluster 3. In the actual scenario, the researcher first coordinated with the respective school principals to confirm the schedule, venue, and appropriate time for the administration of the survey instruments so that the conduct of the study would not disrupt classes and other school activities. Upon arrival at each school, the researcher formally presented the approved communication letters and briefly explained the purpose of the study, the target respondents, and the specific procedures to be followed during the administration of the questionnaires. This initial coordination established a professional and respectful relationship with the school administrators and ensured that the data-gathering activity was properly facilitated within the school setting.

After the necessary coordination, the researcher was endorsed to the identified Home Economics teachers who served as the respondents of the study. Before distributing the questionnaires, the researcher gathered the participants in an appropriate and convenient location, such as a faculty room, vacant classroom, or designated meeting area approved by the school administration. At this stage, the researcher clearly explained the objectives of the study, the significance of their participation, the voluntary nature of their involvement, and the assurance that their responses would be treated with strict confidentiality. The respondents were also informed that they could seek clarification on any part of the questionnaire and that they had the right to decline participation or withdraw at any time without penalty. This actual procedure ensured that ethical considerations were observed before the commencement of the survey proper.

During the distribution of the survey instruments, the researcher personally handed a copy of the questionnaire to each respondent to ensure that the intended participants received the instrument directly. The researcher remained present throughout the process to

provide immediate guidance and clarification whenever respondents encountered items that required further explanation. However, care was taken not to influence their answers, so the researcher's role was limited to explaining instructions and clarifying the meaning of statements when necessary. This hands-on approach helped minimize confusion, promoted accuracy in responses, and ensured that the respondents completed the instrument based on their own actual experiences and perceptions regarding the variables under study.

As the teachers accomplished the questionnaires, the researcher maintained a respectful and non-intrusive presence, allowing the respondents sufficient time to answer thoughtfully and honestly. Since the respondents were teachers with work responsibilities, the instrument was administered with sensitivity to their schedules, ensuring participation was convenient and not burdensome. In some cases, the researcher patiently waited while respondents completed the questionnaire; in other instances, a brief, agreed-upon retrieval time was observed during the same visit, depending on participants' availability. This practical and flexible arrangement reflected the researcher's consideration for the professional responsibilities of the respondents while still maintaining the efficiency of the data-gathering process.

Immediately after the completion of the questionnaires, the researcher personally retrieved the accomplished instruments from each respondent. This prompt collection was important in safeguarding the documents from possible loss, misplacement, or unauthorized access. Upon retrieval, the researcher checked each questionnaire only for completeness of responses, without examining or judging the content in the presence of the respondents, in order to preserve their privacy and avoid any discomfort. If some items were unintentionally left unanswered, the respondent was politely informed and given the choice to complete

the missing portions. This careful retrieval and checking procedure strengthened the completeness, reliability, and integrity of the collected data.

In the final stage, the collected data were subjected to statistical analysis with the assistance of a qualified statistician. The analysis employed the methodologies outlined in the preceding sections of the study, thereby ensuring consistency between the research design and data treatment. The outcomes of the statistical procedures were interpreted in light of the study's objectives, providing meaningful insights into the relationship between technological integration and pedagogical competence. These findings served as the empirical foundation for drawing conclusions and making recommendations that contributed to both theory and practice in the field of Home Economics education.

2.6. Statistical Treatment—The study used the respondents' collected data for analysis. The following statistical tools were used in the analysis and interpretation of the responses in this study to uncover meaningful insights from collected data.

Mean. To determine the extent of technological integration ability and the level of pedagogical competence, descriptive statistics such as the mean were used to summarize the teachers' responses across indicators including digital tools, lesson planning, instructional strategies, and classroom management. Descriptive methods not only provided a clear profile of the data but also facilitated the identification of patterns and trends that captured the teachers' technological practices and pedagogical competence levels (Creswell & Creswell, 2019). These results served as the foundation for interpreting how teachers' experiences with technology reflected their teaching practices.

Pearson Moment Correlation Coefficient. Beyond descriptive measures, the study employed inferential statistics to test the relationship between the two primary variables: tech-

nological integration and pedagogical competence. Pearson R Correlation analysis was used to examine whether a significant association existed between the teachers' ability to integrate technology and their pedagogical competence indicators, such as instructional strategies and assessment practices. This aligned with the study's third objective, which sought to establish whether improvements in technological integration were linked with enhanced pedagogical effectiveness. Inferential procedures provided statistical evidence to validate or refute the hypothesized relationships, ensuring that conclusions were not based merely on descriptive observations but on scientifically tested linkages (Gay et al., 2020).

Multiple Linear Regression. Finally, to address whether specific indicators of technological integration significantly influenced peda-

gogical competence, regression analysis was employed. This statistical approach enabled the identification of predictors, such as the use of digital tools or learner-centered applications, that had a measurable effect on pedagogical competence outcomes. Multiple Linear Regression (MLR) analysis enhanced the study's explanatory power by identifying which dimensions of technological integration contributed most strongly to teachers' pedagogical competence, thereby guiding recommendations for professional development and policy interventions (Saunders et al., 2019).

In sum, the systematic application of descriptive, correlational, and regression analyses ensured methodological rigor and generated meaningful insights into how technology supported and transformed teaching practices in Home Economics education.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the results and discussions based on the data gathered after the conduct of this study. This includes the interpretation of the data and the repercussions of the findings of the study. The deliberations presented in this chapter are aligned to the statement of the problem cited in the previous chapters of this study.

3.1. Extent of Technological Integration Ability of Public Secondary Home Economics Teachers—Summary of the Extent of Technological Integration Ability of Public Secondary Home Economics Teachers. Shown in Table 1 is the summary of the extent of technological integration ability of public secondary Home Economics teachers in Cluster 3, Division of Davao City across four key indicators such as use of digital tools and resources, integration of technology in lesson planning, technological proficiency and skills, and learner-centered technology applications.

The overall mean score of 3.89, a standard deviation (SD) of 0.14, and interpreted as High,

means that the technological integration of public secondary HE teachers in Cluster 3, Division of Davao City are often evident. This indicates that the HE teachers generally demonstrate a strong level of competence in integrating technology into their instructional practices. This suggests that technology is not only present but is meaningfully embedded in teaching and learning processes. The relatively low standard deviation further implies consistency among respondents, indicating a shared level of technological integration across the group. This finding reflects the growing emphasis on digital transformation in education, where teachers are expected to integrate technology effectively to support learning outcomes (OECD, 2023).

Table 1. Summary of the Extent of Technological Integration Ability of Public Secondary Home Economics Teachers

Indicators	Mean	SD	Descriptive Level
Use of Digital Tools and Resources	3.36	0.29	Moderate
Integration of Technology in Lesson Planning	3.74	0.26	High
Technological Proficiency and Skills	4.20	0.24	Very High
Learner-Centered Technology Applications	4.25	0.30	Very High
Overall	3.89	0.14	High

Note. Scale interpretation follows the manuscript: 1.00–1.79 = Very Low; 1.80–2.59 = Low; 2.60–3.39 = Moderate; 3.40–4.19 = High; 4.20–5.00 = Very High, unless otherwise indicated.

Specifically, the indicator on learner-centered technology applications recorded the highest mean score of 4.25, an SD of 0.30, and interpreted as Very High. This means that the technological integration of public secondary HE teachers in Cluster 3, Division of Davao City in terms of learner-centered technology applications are always evident. This demonstrates that the HE teachers are highly capable of using digital tools to foster active, participatory, and learner-centered learning environments. The strong emphasis on learner-centered approaches suggests that HE teachers are shifting from traditional teacher-directed methods toward more constructivist practices, where learners engage in collaborative, inquiry-based, and experiential learning facilitated by technology. Research supports that such approaches significantly enhance learner engagement, motivation, and deeper learning (Crompton & Burke, 2023).

Similarly, technological proficiency and skills obtained a very high mean score of 4.20 with an SD of 0.24. This means that the technological integration of public secondary HE teachers in Cluster 3, Division of Davao City in terms of technological proficiency and skills are always evident. This result indicates that the HE teachers possess strong digital competencies necessary for effective instructional delivery. This further suggests that the HE teachers are confident in operating digital tools, troubleshooting basic technical issues, and utilizing

productivity software to support teaching tasks. Studies have shown that teachers’ digital competence is a key determinant of successful technology integration and innovation in the classroom (Siddiq et al., 2022).

On the other hand, integration of technology in lesson planning yielded a mean score of 3.74, an SD of 0.26, and interpreted as High. This means that the technological integration of public secondary HE teachers in Cluster 3, Division of Davao City in terms of integration of technology in lesson planning are often evident. This indicates that the HE teachers are able to incorporate technology into their instructional planning processes, although not at the same level as their proficiency and learner-centered applications. While technology is integrated into lesson plans, there may still be opportunities to enhance alignment with curriculum standards and optimize the use of digital tools in achieving learning objectives. Literature suggests that effective lesson planning with technology requires not only technical skills but also pedagogical and curricular alignment to maximize instructional effectiveness (Falloon, 2020).

The use of digital tools and resources recorded the lowest mean score of 3.36, an SD of 0.29, and interpreted as Moderate. This means that the technological integration of public secondary Home Economics teachers in Cluster 3, Division of Davao City in terms of the use of digital tools and resources is some-

Table 2. Summary of the Extent of Pedagogical Competence of Public Secondary Home Economics Teachers

Indicators	Mean	SD	Descriptive Level
Instructional Strategies and Methods	4.60	0.21	Very High
Classroom Management and Learner Engagement	4.43	0.24	Very High
Assessment and Evaluation Practices	4.11	0.32	High
Overall	4.38	0.16	Very High

Note. Scale interpretation follows the manuscript: 1.00–1.79 = Very Low; 1.80–2.59 = Low; 2.60–3.39 = Moderate; 3.40–4.19 = High; 4.20–5.00 = Very High, unless otherwise indicated.

times evident. This suggests that while the HE teachers are capable of integrating technology, the actual utilization of diverse digital tools and resources may be limited. Possible factors include inadequate access to technology, insufficient institutional support, or lack of exposure to a wide range of digital platforms. Research indicates that access to digital resources and institutional support significantly influence the extent of technology integration in classrooms (Pettersson, 2021).

The overall mean score of 4.38, a standard deviation (SD) of 0.16, and interpreted as Very High, means that the pedagogical competence of public secondary HE teachers in Cluster 3, Division of Davao City are always evident. This result indicates that the HE teachers consistently demonstrate strong pedagogical competence in delivering instruction. The relatively low standard deviation suggests a high level of consistency among respondents, reflecting a shared capacity in implementing effective teaching practices. This finding highlights that teachers are well-equipped with the necessary pedagogical skills to facilitate meaningful learning experiences, aligning with current educational standards that emphasize quality teaching as a key determinant of learner success (UNESCO, 2022).

Among the indicators, instructional strategies and methods obtained the highest mean

3.2. *Extent of Pedagogical Competence of Public Secondary Home Economics Teachers—* Summary of the Extent of Pedagogical Competence of Public Secondary Home Economics Teachers. Shown in Table 2 is the summary of the extent of pedagogical competence of public secondary Home Economics teachers in Cluster 3, Division of Davao City across three key indicators such as instructional strategies and methods, classroom management and learner engagement, and assessment and evaluation practices.

score of 4.60, an SD of 0.21, and interpreted as High. This means that the pedagogical competence of public secondary HE teachers in Cluster 3, Division of Davao City in terms of instructional strategies and methods are always evident. This indicates that the HE teachers are highly effective in employing diverse teaching approaches that address varying learner needs, promote active participation, and integrate experiential learning. The strong performance in this area reflects teachers’ ability to design and implement instruction that is both engaging and responsive to learners. Research supports that the use of varied and evidence-based instructional strategies significantly enhances learners’ understanding and academic performance, particularly when aligned with learner-centered pedagogies (Muijs et al., 2021).

Classroom management and learner engagement ranked second with a mean score of 4.43,

an SD of 0.24, and also interpreted as Very High. This means that the pedagogical competence of public secondary HE teachers in Cluster 3, Division of Davao City in terms of classroom management and learner engagement are always evident. This suggests that HE teachers are proficient at maintaining structured and positive learning environments while fostering active learner participation. Effective classroom management is essential in ensuring that instructional time is maximized and that learners remain engaged in learning activities. The high rating indicates that the HE teachers are capable of balancing discipline and engagement, which is crucial in both traditional and technology-enhanced classrooms. Literature highlights that strong classroom management practices are closely linked to improved learner behavior, engagement, and academic achievement (Wang et al., 2020).

Assessment and evaluation practices recorded the lowest mean score of 4.11, an SD of 0.32, and interpreted as High. This means that the pedagogical competence of public secondary HE teachers in Cluster 3, Division of Davao City in terms of assessment and evaluation practices are often evident. Although still at a commendable level, this suggests that assessment practices may require further strengthening compared to other pedagogical domains. This may indicate challenges in aligning assessments with learning outcomes, providing timely feedback, or utilizing data effectively to inform instruction. Research emphasizes that effective assessment practices, including formative assessment and data-driven decision-making, are critical for enhancing learner learning and guiding instructional improvement (Black & Wiliam, 2021).

3.3. *Significant Relationship between the Technological Integration and Pedagogical Competence of Public Secondary Home Economics Teachers*—Shown in Table 3 is the statistical analysis using Pearson correlation coefficient

(r) on the significant relationship between technological integration and pedagogical competence of public secondary HE Teachers in Cluster 3, Division of Davao City. This analysis aims to determine whether the extent technological integration among public secondary HE teachers is associated with their pedagogical competence. The correlation coefficients (r -values) indicate the strength and direction of the relationships, while the p -values reveal the statistical significance of these relationships.

The correlation results presented in Table 3 reveal the significant relationship between technological integration and pedagogical competence among public secondary HE teachers in Cluster 3, Division of Davao City, with an overall correlation coefficient of $r = 0.486$, and a p -value of 0.000, indicating a moderate positive and statistically significant relationship. This analysis leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis which implies that higher levels of technological integration are associated with improved pedagogical competence. The descriptive summary in Table 1 supports this finding, as most indicators of technological integration were rated high to very high, particularly in technological proficiency and skills (mean = 4.20), and learner-centered technology applications (mean = 4.25). These findings suggest that since public secondary HE teachers in Cluster 3, Division of Davao City are more adept in using technology and integrating it into learner-centered practices, then they tend to demonstrate stronger pedagogical effectiveness. This aligns with research emphasizing that digital competence enhances instructional quality and supports effective teaching practices (Redecker & Punie, 2020).

Specifically, the use of digital tools and resources with correlation coefficient of $r = 0.356$, a p -value of 0.000 showed a significant moderate positive relationship with pedagogical competence. However, the descriptive summary in Table 1 indicates that this indicator was only rated moderate overall (mean = 3.36), with a

Table 3. Significant Relationship between the Technological Integration and Pedagogical Competence of Public Secondary Home Economics Teachers

Pedagogical Competence		Technological Integration		
	r	p -value	Decision on H ₀	
Use of Digital Tools and Resources	0.356	0.000	Reject	
Integration of Technology in Lesson Planning	0.162	0.101	Failed to Reject	
Technological Proficiency and Skills	0.237	0.016	Reject	
Learner-Centered Technology Applications	0.228	0.021	Reject	
Overall	0.486	0 .000	Reject	

Note. Scale interpretation follows the manuscript: 1.00–1.79 = Very Low; 1.80–2.59 = Low; 2.60–3.39 = Moderate; 3.40–4.19 = High; 4.20–5.00 = Very High, unless otherwise indicated.

notable weakness in the use of online platforms such as LMS and Google Classroom (mean = 1.50, very low). This suggests that while public secondary HE teachers in Cluster 3, Division of Davao City utilize certain digital tools like multimedia presentations, the limited use of more advanced or interactive platforms may

Similarly, technological proficiency and skills with correlation coefficient of $r = 0.237$, and a p-value of 0.016 demonstrated a significant positive relationship with pedagogical competence. The descriptive summary in Table 1 indicates that this indicator was rated very high (mean = 4.20), reflecting teachers' strong confidence in operating digital tools, troubleshooting technical issues, and adapting to new technologies. This suggests that since public secondary HE teachers in Cluster 3, Division of Davao City possess higher levels of technological competence, then they are better equipped to integrate digital tools effectively into their teaching practices. Research consistently highlights that teacher proficiency in technology is a critical determinant of successful integration and improved instructional outcomes (Redecker & Punie, 2020).

Moreover, learner-centered technology applications with correlation coefficient of $r =$

have constrained the strength of its relationship with pedagogical competence. Studies suggest that effective use of diverse digital tools, particularly interactive and collaborative platforms, significantly enhances instructional delivery and learner engagement, which are key components of pedagogical competence (Selwyn, 2021).

0.228, a p-value of 0.021 also exhibited a significant positive relationship with pedagogical competence. Table 1 shows a very high mean (4.25), indicating that public secondary HE teachers in Cluster 3, Division of Davao City actively use technology to promote learner participation, collaboration, and real-world application of knowledge. This finding highlights the importance of using technology not only as a delivery tool but as a means to facilitate active learning and learner engagement. Educational research supports that learner-centered approaches, when combined with appropriate technological tools, significantly enhance teaching effectiveness and foster deeper learning experiences (UNESCO, 2022).

In contrast, integration of technology in lesson planning with correlation coefficient of $r = 0.162$, and a p-value of 0.101 was found to have no significant relationship with pedagogical competence, as indicated by the failure to

Table 4. Regression Analysis of Technological Integration on the Pedagogical Competence of Public Secondary Home Economics Teachers

Predictors	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.	Decision on H0
(Constant)	2.308	.404		5.717	.000	
Use of Digital Tools and Resources	.173	.048	.321	3.618	.000	Reject
Integration of Technology in Lesson Planning	.128	.053	.214	2.410	.018	Reject
Technological Proficiency and Skills	.131	.059	.198	2.213	.029	Reject
Learner-Centered Technology Applications	.109	.047	.206	2.313	.023	Reject

Note. Dependent variable: Pedagogical Competence. R = 0.493; R² = 0.243; F-value = 7.853; p-value = .000.

reject the null hypothesis. Although Table 1 shows a high overall mean (3.74), the descriptive data reveal inconsistencies, particularly in aligning technology with curriculum standards (mean = 1.85, low) and only moderate integration in lesson preparation. These gaps suggest that while public secondary HE teachers in Cluster 3, Division of Davao City may include technology in lesson plans, their integration may not be systematically aligned with instructional objectives or curricular requirements, thereby limiting its impact on pedagogical competence. This finding supports existing literature which emphasizes that the effectiveness of technology integration depends not merely on inclusion but on purposeful alignment with pedagogy and curriculum (Tondeur et al., 2021).

*3.4. Regression Analysis of Technological Integration on the Pedagogical Competence of Public Secondary Home Economics Teachers—*The regression results presented in Table 4 examine the influence of technological integration on the pedagogical competence of public secondary Home Economics teachers in Cluster 3,

The Use of Digital Tools and Resources emerged as the strongest predictor of pedagogical competence ($\beta = .321$, $t = 3.618$, $p = .000$).

Division of Davao City. The analysis yielded an R value of 0.493 and an R² of 0.243, indicating that approximately 24.3% of the variance in pedagogical competence is explained by the combined predictors of technological integration. The F-value of 7.853 with a p-value of .000 confirms that the regression analysis is statistically significant, suggesting that technological integration, as a whole, has a meaningful effect on pedagogical competence. This implies that while other factors may also contribute to teaching effectiveness, the integration of technology remains a significant determinant of pedagogical quality in contemporary education. This finding is consistent with recent studies emphasizing that technology integration enhances instructional effectiveness and supports innovative teaching practices (OECD, 2023). Moreover, all of the indicators of technological integration significantly influence the pedagogical competence of public HE teachers in Cluster 3, Division of Davao City, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis.

This indicates that public secondary HE teachers in Cluster 3, Division of Davao City frequently and effectively utilize digital tools such

as multimedia presentations, online platforms, and interactive applications that is why they tend to demonstrate higher levels of instructional competence. The finding supports existing literature that emphasizes the transformative role of digital resources in improving lesson delivery, enhancing learner engagement, and facilitating differentiated instruction (Falloon, 2020).

4. Summary of Findings, Conclusions and Recommendations

Presented in this chapter are the findings of the study based on the outcome of the gathered data. The conclusions drawn from the findings of the study are likewise outlined in this section. To maximize the significant contribution of this study, the researcher laid down recommendations in this chapter.

4.1. Summary of Findings—Technological integration has become essential in shaping effective teaching and learning, particularly in practice-oriented fields such as Home Economics (HE). When appropriately harnessed, the use of technology promotes learner-centered learning, creativity, and adaptability. While technology promises to enrich HE pedagogy by bridging traditional skill-based instruction with interactive, competency-driven strategies, teachers often encounter barriers related to training, access, and readiness. This study is focused on examining the extent of technological integration ability and its influence on the pedagogical competence of public secondary Home Economics teachers in Cluster 3, Division of Davao City. Anchored on contemporary educational frameworks that emphasize the role of technology in enhancing teaching and learning, the study investigated four key indicators of technological integration such as the use of digital tools and resources, integration of technology in lesson planning, technological proficiency and skills, and learner-centered technology applications. It further assessed pedagogical competence across instructional strategies and methods, classroom management and learner engagement, and assessment and evaluation practices.

Using a quantitative-descriptive correlational research design, the study gathered data

through a structured survey questionnaire administered to public secondary Home Economics teachers. Descriptive statistics such as mean and standard deviation were used to determine the levels of technological integration and pedagogical competence, while inferential statistics, particularly Pearson correlation and regression analysis, were employed to examine relationships and predictive effects. The findings revealed that teachers generally demonstrated high to very high levels of technological integration and very high pedagogical competence, indicating a strong capacity to integrate technology into instructional practices effectively.

Moreover, the study established a significant positive relationship between technological integration and pedagogical competence, confirming that teachers who are more adept in using digital technologies tend to exhibit higher levels of teaching effectiveness. Regression results further indicated that all domains of technological integration significantly influenced pedagogical competence, with the use of digital tools and resources emerging as the strongest predictor. These findings highlight the critical role of technology in enhancing instructional quality and underscore the need for continuous professional development, improved access to digital resources, and strategic integration of technology to further strengthen teaching practices in

Home Economics education.

4.2. *Conclusions*—Based on the findings of this study, the following conclusions were offered:

The extent of technological integration ability of public secondary Home Economics teachers in Cluster 3, Division of Davao City was found to be generally high, indicating that technology integration is often evident in instructional practices. Teachers demonstrated very high levels in technological proficiency and learner-centered applications, suggesting strong digital competence and the ability to use technology to promote active learning. However, the moderate level in the use of digital tools and resources, particularly the very low utilization of online platforms, reveals existing gaps in maximizing available technologies. This implies that while the HE teachers possess the skills and awareness of digital integration, limitations in access, training, or systemic support hinder the full optimization of digital tools in teaching.

The pedagogical competence of public secondary HE teachers in Cluster 3, Division of Davao City was determined to be very high overall, indicating that effective teaching practices are consistently demonstrated. The HE teachers excelled particularly in instructional strategies and methods, as well as classroom management and learner engagement, reflecting strong capabilities in delivering lessons and maintaining productive learning environments. Assessment and evaluation practices, although rated high, emerged as the comparatively weakest domain, suggesting a need to further enhance alignment of assessments with learning outcomes and the use of data-driven approaches. Overall, HE teachers in Cluster 3, Division of Davao City are pedagogically competent and capable of facilitating meaningful and engaging learning experiences.

There is a statistically significant and moderate positive relationship between technological integration ability and pedagogical compe-

tence of public secondary HE teachers in Cluster 3, Division of Davao City. This indicates that higher levels of technological integration are associated with improved teaching effectiveness. Specifically, these HE teachers who are more proficient in using digital tools, applying learner-centered technologies, and demonstrating strong ICT skills tend to exhibit higher pedagogical competence. However, the lack of significant relationship in the integration of technology in lesson planning suggests that mere inclusion of technology in plans does not automatically translate to improved teaching unless it is purposefully aligned with pedagogy and curriculum.

All identified indicators of technological integration such as the use of digital tools and resources, integration in lesson planning, technological proficiency and skills, and learner-centered technology applications were found to significantly influence pedagogical competence, as confirmed by the regression analysis. Among these, the use of digital tools and resources emerged as the strongest predictor, indicating that actual utilization of technology in instruction has the greatest impact on teaching effectiveness. This suggests that practical engagement with digital tools, combined with technical competence and learner-centered application, enhances pedagogical performance. Therefore, strengthening access to digital resources, improving training on advanced platforms, and reinforcing curriculum-aligned integration strategies are essential to further elevate teachers' pedagogical competence.

4.3. *Recommendations*—The following interventions were offered based on the conclusions of the study:

Teachers. Home Economics teachers in Cluster 3, Division of Davao City may strengthen their utilization of diverse digital tools, particularly online platforms such as LMS and collaborative applications, which were found to be underutilized despite high tech-

nological proficiency. This means that teachers must prioritize the adoption of collaborative online platforms to address the "Very Low" utilization identified in this area. They may also focus on aligning technology integration with curriculum standards and improving assessment practices through data-driven strategies. Continuous professional development and self-directed learning in emerging technologies are essential to bridge the gap between existing competence and optimal classroom application.

Learners. Learners in Cluster 3, Division of Davao City may actively engage with digital platforms and take responsibility for their own learning through technology. Given the limited use of online platforms, learners may be provided opportunities to develop digital literacy, collaborative skills, and independent learning habits. Schools may also empower learners to maximize available technologies for research, communication, and skill development, thereby enhancing their participation in technology-enhanced learning environments.

Department of Education Officials. The Department of Education (DepEd) officials in the Division of Davao City may prioritize policies and programs that address infrastructure limitations and provide equitable access to digital tools and reliable internet connectivity. Furthermore, large-scale and sustained professional development programs may be implemented, focusing on advanced digital integration, cur-

riculum alignment, and assessment literacy. Strengthening institutional support systems may ensure that teachers can effectively translate their technological competence into improved pedagogical outcomes.

School Administrators. School administrators in Cluster 3, Division of Davao City may establish strong support mechanisms such as technical assistance teams, monitoring systems, and collaborative learning communities to promote effective technology integration. Administrators may also ensure the availability of digital resources and provide opportunities for capacity-building programs that emphasize curriculum-aligned technology use and inclusive teaching practices. Encouraging a culture of innovation and continuous improvement will help address gaps in technology utilization and assessment practices.

Future Researchers. Finally, future studies may explore other variables that may influence pedagogical competence beyond technological integration, as the current study explains only a portion of the variance. Researchers may also investigate barriers to the use of online platforms, the effectiveness of specific digital tools, and the longitudinal impacts of technology integration. Expanding the scope to different subject areas, regions, or mixed-method approaches will provide a more comprehensive understanding of technology integration in education.

5. References

- Aboagye, E., Yawson, J. A., & Appiah, K. N. (2021). Covid-19 and e-learning: The challenges of learners in tertiary institutions [Social Education Research, 2(1), 1–8.].
- Adeoye, F. A., & Adeoye, T. O. (2020). Availability, adequacy and utilization of instructional materials as predictors of learners' learning outcomes in secondary schools [International Journal of Education and Practice, 8(1), 134–148.].
- Alonzo, D., Bejano, J., & Labad, V. (2023). Alignment between teachers' assessment practices and principles of outcomes-based education in the context of philippine education reform [International Journal of Instruction, 16(1), 489–506.].
- Alonzo, D., Labad, V., & Guerra, G. (2021). The policy-driven dimensions of teacher beliefs about assessment: A critical analysis [Australian Journal of Teacher Education, 46(3), 37–58.].
- Al-Samarraie, H., & Saeed, N. (2021). A systematic review of cloud computing tools for collaborative learning: Opportunities and challenges [Computers & Education, 163, 104099.].
- Babbie, E. (2021). The practice of social research (15th ed.) [Cengage Learning.].
- Bakar, A., & Latip, H. B. A. (2019). The impact of technology integration on teaching and learning in technical and vocational education [Journal of Technical Education and Training, 11(4), 1–13.].
- Beauchamp, T. L., & Childress, J. F. (2019). Principles of biomedical ethics (8th ed.) [Oxford University Press.].
- Bedenlier, S., Bond, M., Buntins, K., Zawacki-Richter, O., & Kerres, M. (2020). Facilitating learner engagement through educational technology: A systematic review in higher education [Australasian Journal of Educational Technology, 36(4), 173–199.].
- Black, P., & Wiliam, D. (2021). Classroom assessment and pedagogy [Assessment in Education: Principles, Policy & Practice, 28(6), 716–731.].
- Blau, I., Shamir-Inbal, T., & Avdiel, O. (2020). How does the pedagogical design of a technology-enhanced collaborative academic course promote digital literacies, self-regulation, and perceived learning of learners? the internet and higher education, 45, 100722.
- Blömeke, S., & Kaiser, G. (2020). Understanding the development of teachers' professional competencies as personally, situationally and socially determined [International Journal of Educational Research, 100, 101529.].
- Bond, M. (2020). Facilitating learner engagement through the flipped learning approach in k-12: A systematic review [Educational Research Review, 31, 100318.].
- Boud, D., & Dawson, P. (2021). What feedback literate teachers do: An empirically-derived competency framework [Assessment & Evaluation in Higher Education, 46(2), 158–171.].
- Bozkurt, A., & Sharma, R. C. (2020). Emergency remote teaching in a time of global crisis due to coronavirus pandemic [Asian Journal of Distance Education, 15(1), 1–6.].
- Cahapay, M. B. (2020). Reshaping assessment practices in a philippine teacher education institution during the covid-19 crisis [Pedagogical Research, 5(4), em0079.].
- Cajilig, E. (2021). Challenges of ict integration in teaching home economics in philippine secondary schools [Philippine Journal of Education Studies, 94(2), 33–48.].

- Clemente, J. A. (2020). Ict competency level of teachers in pampanga: Basis for training program [Journal of Education, Management and Development Studies, 1(1), 15–24].
- Cohen, L., Manion, L., & Morrison, K. (2021). Research methods in education (9th ed.) [Routledge].
- Collin, J., & Quigley, A. (2021). Teacher feedback to improve pupil learning: Guidance report [Education Endowment Foundation].
- Creswell, J. W., & Creswell, J. D. (2019). Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches (5th ed.) [SAGE Publications].
- Crompton, H., & Burke, D. (2023). Artificial intelligence in education: The emerging landscape of teaching and learning [Computers and Education: Artificial Intelligence, 4, 100111].
- Daniel, S. J. (2019). Education and the covid-19 pandemic [Prospects, 49(1), 91–96. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11125-020-09464-3>].
- Daquiado, E. (2022). Ict-based instructional planning among public school teachers in davao region [Mindanao Journal of Education, 5(1), 77–92].
- Darling-Hammond, L., Flook, L., Cook-Harvey, C., Barron, B., & Osher, D. (2020). Implications for educational practice of the science of learning and development [Applied Developmental Science, 24(2), 97–140].
- David, A. M., Sumalinog, K., & Yazon, A. D. (2021). Technological competence and ict integration of teachers in philippine secondary schools [International Journal of Learning, Teaching and Educational Research, 20(8), 204–219].
- Dela Cruz, R. M., & Javier, A. R. (2021). Faculty ict competence and challenges in higher education institutions [International Journal of Education Research for Higher Learning, 27(2), 45–60].
- Emanuel, E. J., Wendler, D., & Grady, C. (2019). An ethical framework for biomedical research [The Oxford Textbook of Clinical Research Ethics, 123–135. Oxford University Press].
- Falloon, G. (2020). From digital literacy to digital competence: The teacher digital competency framework [Educational Technology Research and Development, 68, 2449–2472].
- Florian, L., & Black-Hawkins, K. (2021). Exploring inclusive pedagogy [Cambridge Journal of Education, 51(3), 1–15].
- Fraenkel, J. R., Wallen, N. E., & Hyun, H. H. (2021). How to design and evaluate research in education (11th ed.) [McGraw-Hill Education].
- Frailon, J., Ainley, J., Schulz, W., Friedman, T., & Duckworth, D. (2023). International computer and information literacy study (icils) 2023: Preparing for life in a digital world [International Association for the Evaluation of Educational Achievement (IEA)].
- Gay, L. R., Mills, G. E., & Airasian, P. W. (2020). Educational research: Competencies for analysis and applications (12th ed.) [Pearson].
- Ghavifekr, S., & Rosdy, W. A. W. (2020). Teaching and learning with technology: Effectiveness of ict integration in schools [International Journal of Research in Education and Science, 6(1), 175–191].
- Gikandi, J. W., Morrow, D., & Davis, N. E. (2020). Online formative assessment in higher education: A review of the literature [Computers & Education, 71, 233–251].
- Guerriero, S. (2020). Pedagogical knowledge and the changing nature of the teaching profession [European Journal of Teacher Education, 43(4), 457–471].

- Habibu, T., Abdullah-Al-Mamun, M., & Clement, C. K. (2020). The integration of ict in teaching and learning: Teachers' attitudes and challenges [International Journal of Education and Development using ICT, 16(2), 144–157.].
- Hattie, J. (2023). Visible learning: The sequel [Routledge.].
- Huck, S. W. (2019). Reading statistics and research (7th ed.) [Pearson.].
- Instefjord, E. J., & Munthe, E. (2020). Preparing teachers for digital competence: A systematic review of teacher education [Teaching and Teacher Education, 90, 103030.].
- Iphofen, R. (2022). Handbook of research ethics and scientific integrity [Springer.].
- Kaliisa, R., & Picard, M. (2021). Mobile learning policy and practice in higher education: A systematic review [Computers & Education, 170, 104239.].
- Kerimbayev, N., Abdykarimova, S., & Akramova, A. (2023). Digital learning technologies in higher education: Tools for competence development [Education and Information Technologies, 28, 2045–2062.].
- Kimmons, R., Graham, C. R., & West, R. E. (2020). The picrat model for technology integration in teacher preparation [Contemporary Issues in Technology and Teacher Education, 20(1), 176–198.].
- Koehler, M. J., Mishra, P., & Cain, W. (2019). What is technological pedagogical content knowledge (tpack)? journal of education, 193(3), 13–19.
- König, J., Blömeke, S., Jentsch, A., Schlesinger, L., & Kaiser, G. (2020). The links between pedagogical competence, instructional quality, and learner development: A longitudinal study of teacher education [Teaching and Teacher Education, 95, 103127. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2020.103127>].
- König, J., Jäger-Biela, D. J., & Glutsch, N. (2020). Adapting to online teaching during covid-19: School teachers' competencies and professional development [European Journal of Teacher Education, 43(4), 608–622.].
- Lau, W. W. F., & Lee, K. C. (2021). Teachers' technological pedagogical content knowledge in hong kong: Implications for teacher professional development [Asia-Pacific Education Researcher, 30(1), 35–45.].
- Lodico, M. G., Spaulding, D. T., & Voegtle, K. H. (2019). Methods in educational research: From theory to practice (3rd ed.) [Jossey-Bass.].
- Magwiro, O., Moyo, N., & Ncube, C. (2021). The integration of icts in home economics education: Opportunities and challenges [International Journal of Home Economics, 14(2), 45–55.].
- Martin, F., & Bolliger, D. U. (2021). Engagement matters: Learner perceptions on the importance of engagement strategies [Online Learning Journal, 25(2), 1–23.].
- Martin, F., Sun, T., & Westine, C. D. (2022). A systematic review of research on online teaching and learning [Educational Technology Research and Development, 70, 1–24.].
- Mayer, R. E. (2021). Multimedia learning (3rd ed.) [Cambridge University Press.].
- McMillan, J. H., & Schumacher, S. (2021). Research in education: Evidence-based inquiry (8th ed.) [Pearson.].
- Mishra, P., & Koehler, M. J. (2019). Introducing technological pedagogical content knowledge [Journal of Computer Assisted Learning, 35(5), 557–563.].
- Morris, R., Perry, T., & Wardle, L. (2021). Formative assessment and feedback for learning in higher education: A systematic review [Review of Education, 9(3), e3292. <https://doi.org/10.1002/rev3.3292>].

- Morris, T. H. (2020). Experiential learning – a systematic review and revision of kolb’s model [Interactive Learning Environments, 28(8), 1064–1077.].
- Muijs, D., Kyriakides, L., van der Werf, G., Creemers, B., Timperley, H., & Earl, L. (2021). State of the art—teacher effectiveness and professional learning [School Effectiveness and School Improvement, 32(1), 1–34.].
- OECD. (2020). Education policy evaluation: Surveying the oecd landscape (edu/wkp(2020)24) [Paris: OECD Publishing.].
- OECD. (2023). Shaping digital education: Enabling factors for quality, equity and efficiency [OECD Publishing.].
- Pagalilauan, R. B. (2021). Assessment literacy of tertiary instructors in davao city retrieved from researchgate.
- Pettersson, F. (2021). On the issues of digital competence in educational contexts—a review of literature [Education and Information Technologies, 26, 1005–1021.].
- Phillipsen, B., Tondeur, J., Pynoo, B., Vanslambrouck, S., Zhu, C., & Lombaerts, K. (2022). Examining teachers’ online professional development: A systematic review [Educational Research Review, 36, 100452.].
- Pokhrel, S., & Chhetri, R. (2021). A literature review on impact of covid-19 pandemic on teaching and learning [Higher Education for the Future, 8(1), 133–141.].
- Quibod, R., & Menez, M. (2021). Ict integration practices among teachers in davao region during the covid-19 pandemic [International Journal of Learning, Teaching and Educational Research, 20(5), 15–29.].
- Ramos, C. A., & Camacho, A. (2020). Integrating ict in home economics: Enhancing entrepreneurial competencies of filipino learners [Philippine Journal of Home Economics Education, 8(1), 22–36.].
- Reddy, S. L., & Bubonia, J. (2020). Learning opportunities for teachers and learners: Family and consumer sciences [Journal of Family and Consumer Sciences, 112(1), 46–50.].
- Redecker, C. (2021). European framework for the digital competence of educators: Digcompedu [Publications Office of the European Union.].
- Redecker, C., & Punie, Y. (2020). European framework for the digital competence of educators (digcompedu) [European Commission.].
- Resnik, D. B. (2020). The ethics of research with human subjects: Protecting people, advancing science, promoting trust [Springer.].
- Sailer, M., Stadler, M., Schultz-Pernice, F., Franke, U., Schöffmann, C., Paniotova, V., & Fischer, F. (2024). Learning activities in technology-enhanced learning: A review of meta-analyses [Computers & Education, 207, 104932.].
- Sanchez, J., & Cruz, M. (2021). Barriers to effective ict use in teaching-learning among davao educators [Mindanao Journal of Education, 4(2), 88–102.].
- Sarmiento, C. P., Morales, M. P. E., Elipane, L. E., & Palomar, B. C. (2020). Assessment practices in philippine higher steam education [Journal of University Teaching & Learning Practice, 17(5), Article 18.].
- Saunders, M., Lewis, P., & Thornhill, A. (2019). Research methods for business learners (8th ed.) [Pearson Education Limited.].
- Schleicher, A. (2020). The impact of covid-19 on education: Insights from education at a glance 2020 [OECD Publishing.].

- Schmid, M., Brianza, E., & Petko, D. (2021). Developing a short questionnaire to measure teachers' tpack [Australasian Journal of Educational Technology, 37(2), 1–16].
- Selwyn, N. (2021). Education and technology: Key issues and debates (3rd ed.) [Bloomsbury Academic.].
- Siddiq, F., Scherer, R., & Tondeur, J. (2022). Teachers' digital competence: A systematic review of assessment instruments [Educational Research Review, 36, 100448.].
- Tejada, J. J., & Punzalan, J. R. B. (2019). On the misuse of slovin's formula [Philippine Statistician, 68(1), 129–136.].
- Tindowen, D. J. (2020). Teachers' professional development in the philippines: The use of ict [International Journal of Learning, Teaching and Educational Research, 19(3), 1–14.].
- Tomlinson, C. A. (2021). How to differentiate instruction in academically diverse classrooms (3rd ed.) [ASCD.].
- Tondeur, J., Scherer, R., Siddiq, F., & Baran, E. (2021). A comprehensive framework for teacher digital competence [Educational Technology Research and Development, 69, 139–160.].
- Trust, T., & Whalen, J. (2020a). Should teachers be trained in emergency remote teaching? lessons learned from covid-19 [Journal of Technology and Teacher Education, 28(2), 189–199.].
- Trust, T., & Whalen, J. (2020b). Should teachers be trained in emergency remote teaching? lessons learned from the covid-19 pandemic [Journal of Technology and Teacher Education, 28(2), 189–199.].
- UNESCO. (2022). Global education monitoring report 2022: Technology in education – a tool on whose terms? unesco publishing.
- Villanueva, G. (2021). Ict integration in home economics instruction: Perspectives of secondary school teachers [Philippine Journal of Teacher Education, 3(2), 55–68.].
- Wang, M.-T., Degol, J. L., & Henry, D. A. (2020). An integrative development-in-sociocultural-context model for children's engagement in learning [American Psychologist, 75(7), 1086–1102.].
- World Health Organization (WHO). (2021). Ethics and covid-19: Resource allocation and priority-setting [WHO Press.].